

Using CRISPR/Cas9 to investigate the developmental roles of *Fcho*, *Pgm3*, and *Nckap1* in *Ciona*, Part 1: guide RNA design and validation

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Introduction

The tunicate *Ciona robusta* (formally *intestinalis* Type A) serves as a convenient chordate model for investigating gene function during embryogenesis [1]. Its simplified body plan, rapid development, and experimental tractability make it an attractive system for exploring fundamental or potentially chordate-specific mechanisms of gene regulation and cellular morphogenesis [2]. CRISPR/Cas9-mediated mutagenesis in *Ciona* has enabled targeted disruption of single genes with high efficiency in F₀ embryos, supporting both basic research and pedagogical applications [3, 4].

With support from Arcadia Science, we are currently studying three genes- *Fcho*, *Pgm3*, and *Nckap1* [5]. These were identified as *Ciona* orthologs of human disease-associated genes and intriguing candidates for further investigation by Arcadia Science's Zoogole platform [6]. In vertebrates, Fcho1 (FCH And Mu Domain Containing Endocytic Adaptor 1) encodes an endocytic adaptor involved in clathrin-mediated vesicle formation [7-9], Pgm3 (Phosphoacetylglucosamine mutase 3) participates in carbohydrate metabolism and glycosylation pathways critical for extracellular matrix integrity [10-13], and Nckap1l (Nck-Associated Protein 1-Like) is part of the WAVE regulatory complex, linking signaling pathways to actin cytoskeleton remodeling [14-16]. Disruption of these genes in humans is associated with diverse developmental and immune disorders, but we lack a more detailed tissue-level understanding of their cellular functions.

As highlighted previously by both bulk and single-cell RNAseq (scRNAseq)[5], all three appear to be expressed during *Ciona* embryonic development. Only *Pgm3* expression has been characterized by *in situ* hybridization, showing strong and specific upregulation in the endoderm and notochord [17]. Although *in situs* for *Fcho* and *Nckap1* are still lacking, by scRNAseq both are also expressed to some extent in endoderm and notochord. Hence, we started focusing on a plan to knock these genes out in endoderm and notochord cell lineages and assay the effects on the proper morphogenesis of these cells and surrounding tissues during embryogenesis.

Here, we report our approach for designing and testing single-chain guide RNAs (sgRNAs) for CRISPR/Cas9-mediated inactivation of each gene. We report the efficacies of each sgRNA in causing target indels, and select the appropriate sgRNA combinations to proceed with *in vivo*, tissue-specific phenotypes in F₀ embryos to be reported in our next installment.

sgRNA design

For each target gene, three sgRNAs were selected (Table 1) using the CRISPOR website (<https://crispor.gi.ucsc.edu/>)[18] following our established *Ciona*-specific strategies that have been previously published [19]. CRISPOR is ideal for researchers working on *Ciona* due to its incorporation of single nucleotide polymorphism (SNP) data, allowing us to avoid potentially polymorphic target sites; *Ciona* populations are known to harbor extreme genetic diversity [20],

and any mismatches between the sgRNA and the target sequence in the actual specimens used in the lab might result in low mutagenesis efficacies.

sgRNA	Doench '16	Doench-RuleSet3	MIT specificity
Fcho 1.34	57	23	100
Fcho 4.63	59	33	100
Fcho 5.112	63	-25	99
Nckap1 2.74	68	63	100
Nckap1 7.36	66	43	100
Nckap1 8.103	60	71	100
Pgm3 1.83	72	81	33*
Pgm3 2.27	60	24	50*
Pgm3 3.31	59	61	100

Table 1. List of sgRNAs tested in this study, and their efficacy and specificity scores as predicted by CRISPOR. Asterisk denote “false” cases of low specificity due to confirmed genome assembly errors.

To search for potential sgRNAs, we typically input the gene’s exons one at a time, starting from exon 1 upwards, until we obtain sgRNAs with high enough predicted efficacies and specificities. High efficacy is typically predicted by high “Doench '16” score [21], specificity by an “MIT specificity” score >99 [22]. We have previously shown correlation between high, actual efficacy and predicted Doench '16 efficacy scores over 50. Thus, our informal predicted efficacy (Doench '16) score cutoff is typically ~50. A new predictive algorithm has been recently incorporated into CRISPOR, named “Doench RuleSet 3” [23]. We do not yet have data to support using these new scores versus the “old” Doench '16 scores for CRISPR in *Ciona*.

To ensure specificity, we aim for MIT specificity scores >99. As the *Ciona robusta* genome is quite small and compact (~120 Mbp), scores of 99 and 100 are quite common and would rule out most potential off-target effects. We have previously detected a low (~5%) mutagenesis rate at a site with perfect sgRNA seed-target match but a non-canonical/alternative protospacer-adjacent motif (PAM)[19]. In theory, we would prefer to avoid sgRNAs that might target similar non-canonical sites, but for now CRISPOR does not allow us to automatically screen for those.

Candidate sgRNAs were chosen to maximize predicted mutagenesis efficiency while minimizing potential off-target activity. We also prioritized targeting sequences encoding the N-terminal region of the resulting protein, to maximize the likelihood of generating null alleles. We must balance the likelihood that a null, or “near-null” allele will result from our CRISPR-mediated indels, with the chance that cutting too close to the start codon will allow for translation of a mostly functional protein from a new, alternate start codon further into the coding sequence.

For Pgm3, we noticed abnormally low MIT specificity scores for sgRNAs targeting the first two exons, but we ascertained that this was due to older genome assembly errors that had erroneously duplicated those Pgm3 sequences. We were able to confirm that these earlier assembly errors were not present in the latest updates “HT” version of the *Ciona robusta* genome assembly [24], thus restoring our confidence in the specificity of these sgRNAs. Indeed, all the predicted off-targets flagged initially were in the incorrect assembly duplicate sequences.

Validating sgRNAs

All sgRNAs were tested according our established protocol ([link to protocols.io](https://www.protocols.io))(Figure 1)[19]. Briefly, each sgRNA is expressed using the U6 small RNA promoter, from plasmid co-electroporated into synchronized *Ciona* zygotes along with *Eef1a>Cas9* plasmid. In this setup, Cas9 and the sgRNA are expressed in most cells. Larvae are then collected after hatching, comprising pools of hundreds or even thousands of F₀ CRISPs. Genomic DNA is extracted from each pool (representing a single sgRNA test), and amplicons centered on the sgRNA target site are obtained by PCR from the resulting genomic DNA. Amplicons (150-450 bp in size) are then sequenced by Illumina sequencing by Genewiz/Azenta, which provides automated indel analysis including estimated mutagenesis efficacy rate. Often the efficacy percentages presented are only approximated due to confounding naturally occurring SNPs and indels. This is because of the high genetic diversity in the wild *Ciona* populations we use for our studies.

Figure 1. Diagram depicting our sgRNA validation workflow. Synchronized *Ciona robusta* zygotes (1-cell-stage embryos) are electroporated with plasmid DNAs to drive near-ubiquitous expression of an sgRNA and Cas9. The sgRNA is transcribed by RNA polymerase III via the small RNA promoter, while Cas9 expression is driven by the *Eef1a* promoter. Co-expression is denoted by purple coloring of cells. Mosaic uptake and/or retention of the plasmids results in some cells that do not express either. Embryos are then left to grow (typically to the larval stage) before pooling and genomic DNA extraction and downstream PCR and sequencing of target site amplicons (see text and linked protocol for details).

For *Fcho*, we tested three sgRNAs targeting exons 1, 3, or 5, surrounding the region that encodes a conserved FCH domain near the N terminus (Figure 2). The most efficacious sgRNAs by indel analysis were sgRNAs 1.34 and 5.112. The efficacy of sgRNA 1.34 was measured at 43%, which is on the higher end of the range of efficacies that we have measured for other sgRNAs in our lab. For sgRNA 5.112, an exact efficacy percentage was not obtained due to a confounding natural SNP, but it was well over 15%. Comparing to 1.34, it was likely to be closer to 30-40%. As such, these two sgRNAs were selected for future use, and sgRNA 4.63 was all but abandoned. When used in combination, sgRNAs 1.34 and 5.112 are also predicted to delete the entire FCH domain at the N terminus, which would further increase the odds of producing a null allele.

Figure 2. Fcho sgRNA validation results

For *Pgm3*, sgRNAs 1.83 and 2.27 had the highest efficacies (Figure 3). Again, the exact efficacy for 1.83 was not measured due to a naturally occurring indel in the amplicon region, but was well over 12%. By looking at the height of the major CRISPR-induced deletion peak, its efficacy appeared roughly equivalent to that of sgRNA 2.27, which was measured at 23%. Both of these sgRNAs target the first two overlapping phosphoglucomutase/phosphomannomutase (PGM/PMM) domains, suggesting that using them in combination will likely produce null alleles. We therefore went ahead and selected these two for further use.

Figure 3. Pgm3 sgRNA validation results

Finally, for *Nckap1* (Figure 4), the presence of extensive natural indels and SNPs prevented an exact measurement of the efficacy of any of our three sgRNAs, but based on comparisons to the *Pgm3*-targeting sgRNAs, we believe that 2.74 and 8.103 were also in the 20-30% range. These target the 2nd and 8th exons of *Nckap1*, respectively. Unlike Fcho or Pgm3, the Nckap1 protein does not have any conserved domains other than the entire protein representing its own domain family. As such, it is not clear what parts of this large protein might be key for its functions, but using the above sgRNAs in combination, a large deletion at the N terminus should likely result in null alleles.

Figure 4. *Nckap1* sgRNA validation results

Future plans

So far our sgRNA designs and validations appear to have been reasonably successful. Anecdotal comparisons to the sgRNAs we have already used in our published papers, we believe our new sgRNAs will be useful to further investigate the functions of these three genes in follow up studies. Our immediate plans are to use the sgRNA combinations outlined above together with endoderm- and notochord-specific Cas9 vectors to generate tissue-specific indels in each gene and assay their effects on embryonic development. We will start by looking at endoderm and notochord morphogenesis, the latter including both convergent extension and vacuolization.

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